

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY

Deliverable 2.8

Parkinson's disease in the eye, first approach

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101137074. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Parkinson's Disease is the second most common neurodegenerative disease in the United States, with no single, definite diagnostic test currently available. Retinal image analysis represents a promising route to ameliorate these issues: the retina being part of the brain motivates the hypothesis that changes in the brain caused by neurodegenerative diseases may have retinal biomarkers identifiable from ophthalmic images.

In this work, we collected a dataset of Optical Coherence Tomography images for both Parkinson's Disease cases (349 patients, 60,132 images) and three control cohorts with a 1:5 image ratio (total images for controls: 300,660): a random group (2,388 subjects), a gender matched group (1,785 subjects), and a gender and age matched group (2,988 subjects).

We trained two deep learning models (ResNet50 and RETFound) to predict which images are taken from patients with Parkinson's, obtaining Area under the ROC curve values of 0.74, 0.62, and 0.53 for RETFound on the random, unmatched cohort, on the gender matched cohort, and on the age and gender matched cohort, respectively. We hypothesized that age could be used by our trained models as a proxy for PD prediction, and we further verified it by computing the Spearman correlation coefficient between age and the models' probability of PD, reporting 0.68, 0.64, and 0.15 for the previously mentioned model and cohorts.

Our initial analysis highlighted the challenges of predicting PD from retinal images, as age represents a strong confounder that can be used as a proxy for the diagnostic task of interest. In the future, we will explore alternative model architectures, training paradigms, and additional data sources in terms of modalities (e.g., clinical notes or EHR data) and institutions (via Federated Learning).

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable ID	D2.8
Deliverable Title	Parkinson's disease in the eye, first approach
Work Package	WP2
Lead Partner	UCD
Due date	30.06.2025
Date of submission	25.06.2025
Type of deliverable	R
Dissemination level	PU

AUTHORS

Name	Organisation
Giacomo Nebbia (Author)	UCD
Jayashree Kalpathy-Cramer (Author)	UCD
Nils Kohn (Internal Reviewer)	RUMC
Anna Romanovych (Contributor)	UNIPD

REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
V0.1	06/06/25	Nils Kohn	Approve, minor comments
V0.2	18/06/25	Giacomo Nebbia	Addressed comments
V1.0	25/06/2025	Anna Romanovych	Finalizing the format of the deliverable

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contents

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
2 METHODS	8
2.1 Dataset.....	9
2.2 Experimental design	10
2.3 Retinal layer segmentation	11
2.4 Implementation	11
3 RESULTS	11
3.1 Age as a confounding factor	12
3.2 Focusing on specific retinal layers	12
4 DISCUSSION	13
5 FUTURE WORK	13
REFERENCES	15

List of Tables

Table 1 Statistics for the collected cases and controls cohorts as number of patients, volumes, and 2D b-scans.	10
Table 2 Test AUC values for our two models (ResNet and RETFound) and for age as a predictor of PD.....	11
Table 3 Spearman correlation between age and probability of PD predicted by our models (for volume level prediction, the image level probabilities for each volume are aggregated with a maximum function).....	12
Table 4 Test AUC for models trained (and evaluated) on RNFL-masked OCT b-scans	13

List of Figures

Figure 1 Our methods' pipeline.....	9
-------------------------------------	---

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Original version
PD	Parkinson's Disease
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
OCT	Optical Coherence Tomography
RNFL	Retinal Nerve Fiber Layer
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
AUC	Area under the ROC Curve
GC-IPL	Ganglion Cell-Inner Plexiform Layer
EHR	Electronic Health Record
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations

1 INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's Diseases (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disease in the United States (after Alzheimer's Disease) (Willis et al., 2022), and the number of people affected by it is estimated to increase by up to 196% in certain age groups by 2050 (Su et al., 2025). Additionally, there does not exist a single, definite test for diagnosing PD and there is currently no way to track disease progression at a biological level (Tolosa et al., 2021).

Ophthalmology represents an interesting possibility to alleviate some of these issues. The retina is part of the brain, as such, it can be hypothesized that changes in the brain due to PD (or other neurodegenerative diseases) could be reflected in retinal changes. This hypothesis is currently being investigated as part of the so called "oculomics" approaches, which more broadly aim at diagnosing systemic diseases from retinal imaging, whether neurodegenerative (Jo et al., 2019) or not (e.g., cardiovascular (Huang et al., 2024)).

Use Case 3 fits in this line of work as it proposed to investigate ways to diagnosed PD from retinal data in a multimodal and multi-centre fashion. This deliverable represents the first step in that direction, providing a first approach to predicting PD from as single data modality (Optical Coherence Tomography images) collected from a single institution (University of Colorado Denver). Future deliverables will explore both additional approaches applied to the same data, as well as combining features from OCT with clinical and demographic information (D2.9 at M36) and including additional centres to, possibly, train foundation models using a self-supervised approach to extract features and classify PD (D2.10 at M48).

2 METHODS

Figure 1 depicts our methods' pipeline including curation of a case-control cohort, training a model to predict PD, and evaluating the trained model.

Figure 1 Our methods' pipeline.

Top: we collect a cohort by matching cases and controls by matching age and gender (notice that each control subject can only be associated with one case patient, hence case3 in the example cannot be matched to control3, visit 2). Bottom left: we finetune a RETFound model and train a ResNet50 on the PD diagnosis task. Bottom right: we evaluate the trained model at image level (i.e., comparing predicted probability of PD for each 2D b-scan with ground truth) and at volume level (i.e., by aggregating all probability for a volume's b-scans by taking the maximum before comparing with the ground truth).

2.1 Dataset

We collected data from the Sue Anschutz-Rodgers Eye Center from the University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus. IRB approval was obtained for this study and patient consent was waived as the study constitutes secondary research and does not present higher than minimal risk for patients. Specifically, we considered OCT macular volumes from Heidelberg Spectralis machines, resulting in a total of 236,019 3D volumes (4,906,485 2D b-scans) for 27,550 patients.

To identify patients diagnosed with PD, we considered their ICD 9 and ICD 10 codes as recorded in their EHR records: if a patient was assigned either code 332.0 (ICD 9) or G20 (ICD 10) or its children (due to the hierarchical nature of ICD 10, G20 is the parent code for all PD-related diagnoses). All images taken at or after the earliest PD diagnosis are considered as "cases", while all images taken before diagnosis are excluded. Alternatively, these images could be considered as "controls", although we would risk some PD-related signal to be in the images due to, for instance, late diagnosis (i.e., retinal signs appeared before clinical diagnosis). This selection results into 349 patients and 2,826 volumes (60,132 2D b-scans).

Finally, we selected a cohort of "controls", defined as patients who were never associated with a PD diagnosis (based on ICD codes as outlined above) and never associated with a diagnosis of Alzheimer's Disease (ICD9/10 codes: 331/G30 and children) or Multiple

Sclerosis (ICD9/10 codes: 340/G35), which represent the two other most frequent neurodegenerative diseases represented in our dataset. We fixed the number of control volumes (and images) to 5 times the number of case volumes, resulting in 14,130 volumes and 300,660 2D b-scans. Furthermore, we selected such volumes by using three matching strategies:

1. **Unmatched:** the volumes are randomly sampled from the overall control pool
2. **Gender matched:** the volumes are matched based on patient gender to ensure an equal male/female distribution between cases and controls
3. **Gender and Age matched:** the volumes are matched based on patient gender and age at the time of image acquisition. Age matching is achieved by finding, for each case volume, a control volume that is the closest in age (in years), for a maximum of 5 years. This constraint is always satisfied thanks to our large pool of potential controls. In addition, each control subject can only be matched to 1 PD patient (to ensure inclusion of as many control patients as possible), although multiple volumes for the same control subject can be matched to multiple volumes for the same PD case (to maximize the number of case volumes that are matched to control volumes).

Table 1 summarized statistics for the collected cases and controls cohorts.

We highlight that our control subjects are not necessarily “healthy” individuals. Specifically, our dataset does not include screening populations (where healthy subjects can be found), but it is limited to patients that were seen in our Ophthalmology clinics due to some ophthalmic complaint. As such, our controls can be diagnosed with ophthalmic diseases including glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy, and age-related macular degeneration (among others).

Table 1 Statistics for the collected cases and controls cohorts as number of patients, volumes, and 2D b-scans.

The number of patients in each control cohort varies due to the number of b-scans in each volume being either 19, 49, or 25.

	N. patients	N. volumes	N. 2D b-scans
Overall	27,550	236,019	4,906,485
PD	349	2,826	60,132
Controls			
Unmatched	2,388	14,130	300,660
Gender matched	1,785		
Gender and Age matched	2,988		

2.2 Experimental design

We experimented with two Deep Learning model architectures:

- ResNet50 (He et al., 2016), a Convolutional Neural Network commonly used in medical and non-medical imaging tasks
- RETFound (Zhou et al., 2023), an OCT-specific foundation model

To train the models, we split the dataset in training/validation/test split at patient level with an 80/10/10 ratio. The models were trained at b-scan level (following the approach used to pre-train RETFound) by assigning the volume's PD status label to each 2D b-scan in the volume.

For evaluation, we used AUC computed at image level and at volume level by taking the maximum predicted probability of PD returned by the model across the 2D b-scans for each volume (we chose the maximum since as long as part of a volume is associated with PD, the whole volume should be as well).

2.3 Retinal layer segmentation

To isolate the contribution of individual retinal layers to PD prediction, we trained a Deep Learning model to segment the Retinal Nerve Fiber Layer (RNFL). We obtained ground truth segmentations from our staff optometrist for 50 random b-scan images from 50 random patients in our overall dataset (none coming from the test splits for our cohorts) and trained a Deep Learning model. We evaluated this model qualitatively on a subset of images unseen during training; thorough quantitative evaluation is underway.

2.4 Implementation

We used the RETFound implementation provided by its developers (https://github.com/rmaphoh/RETFound_MAE) and we extended their code to allow for training of a ResNet50 (instead of RETFound's default Vision Transformer architecture). We trained the models for 10 epochs, with 1 warmup epoch. All other hyperparameters were left unchanged. Models were trained on 4 NVIDIA RTX A4000 GPU servers.

For layer segmentation, we finetuned a MedSAM (Ma et al., 2024) model starting from the weights available on huggingface (<https://huggingface.co/flaviagiammarino/medsam-vit-base>).

3 RESULTS

Table 2 shows the AUC values on the test set for our two models.

Table 2 Test AUC values for our two models (ResNet and RETFound) and for age as a predictor of PD. The AUC of age quantifies the extent to which age is a confounding factor that can potentially be used as a proxy for PD by our models.

	Unmatched		Gender matched		Gender and age matched	
	Image	Volume	Image	Volume	Image	Volume
Age	0.78	0.78	0.69	0.69	0.40	0.40
ResNet50	0.69	0.71	0.67	0.68	0.62	0.49
RETFound	0.74	0.73	0.62	0.64	0.53	0.52

From Table 2, we notice both Deep Learning models having comparable performance (especially at volume level), with RETFound achieving the highest AUC of 0.73 on the unmatched cohort. Importantly, we highlight the fact that performance decreases as we

match for gender and gender and age, with RETFound's performance (at image level) dropping from 0.74 to 0.62 to 0.53, respectively. This suggests a confounding effect of age, which, we hypothesize, is learned by the DL models as a proxy for PD status. We report AUC for age itself as a predictor for PD to showcase how closely our DL models' performance is to that of age: age's AUC drops from 0.78 to 0.69 to 0.40 after matching for gender and gender and age, respectively. An AUC for age of around 0.50 is expected for the age matched cohort since, due to matching, age should not have any correlation with PD status.

3.1 Age as a confounding factor

To further test the hypothesis that age is used by our models as a proxy for PD status, Table 3 shows the Spearman correlation between the predicted probability of PD (at image level and aggregated at volume level with a maximum function) and age at the time of the image.

Table 3 Spearman correlation between age and probability of PD predicted by our models (for volume level prediction, the image level probabilities for each volume are aggregated with a maximum function)

	Unmatched		Gender matched		Gender and age matched	
	Image	Volume	Image	Volume	Image	Volume
ResNet50	0.50	0.60	0.48	0.51	-0.02	0.12
RETFound	0.68	0.71	0.64	0.67	0.15	0.21

From Table 3, we notice moderate correlation between age and predicted probability of PD. Interestingly, this correlation is higher for better performing models (namely, RETFound in the unmatched cohort, whose volume level performance is 0.73 and its Spearman correlation is 0.71). As expected, correlation becomes ~ 0 after matching for age. While these results suggest that age is indeed used as a proxy, non-perfect correlation values also suggest that more, non-age-related signal may exist in the unmatched cohort.

3.2 Focusing on specific retinal layers

Previous studies have shown that thinning of specific retinal layers may be linked to neurodegenerative diseases such as PD or Alzheimer's. To attempt to magnify the PD-specific signal in OCT b-scans, we segmented the RNFL layer and masked the images so that only the pixels associated with it would be visible to the model.

Table 4 reports test AUCs for models trained (and evaluated) on such masked images.

Table 4 Test AUC for models trained (and evaluated) on RNFL-masked OCT b-scans

	Unmatched		Gender matched		Gender and age matched	
	Image	Volume	Image	Volume	Image	Volume
ResNet50	0.51	0.48	0.49	0.41	0.44	0.44
RETFound	0.47	0.48	0.44	0.38	0.41	0.38

From Table 4, we notice very low performance across cohorts, suggesting that the models are not able to extract PD-related signals from the masked images. Furthermore, the low performance on the unmatched cohort also indicates that age-related signal could not be extracted (otherwise, we would expect comparable performance as that reported in Table 2).

4 DISCUSSION

Results for our first approach uncovered the non-negligible confounding factor that age plays in predicting Parkinson’s Disease (and likely other age-related neurodegenerative diseases). Our best performing model on a non age-matched cohort achieves a test AUC of 0.73 at volume level, but PD prediction shows a Spearman correlation with age at time of image of 0.71, suggesting that age is indeed used by the model as a proxy to predict PD.

The ability of Deep Learning models to predict age from medical images (and specifically ophthalmic images) is well documented in the literature (Khan et al., 2022; Rim et al., 2020). It is thus not surprising that our models are able to learn it and use it as a proxy for PD. Additionally, previous work has also noted that age can be a confounding factor when studying neurodegenerative diseases: previous work on finetuning RETFound for 3-year PD risk prediction highlighted how the model performs better when the age gap between cases and controls is wider (Zhou et al., 2023).

In general, previous results on predicting PD from ophthalmic images are mixed: some analysis on layer thinning found no discriminative ability when looking at RNFL and ganglion cell-inner plexiform layer (GC-IPL) with AUC of 0.51 and 0.50, respectively after age matching (Robbins et al., 2021), while others reporting increased hazards ratio for GC-IPL thinning even after age and sex matching (Wagner et al., 2023). Further, others were able to train a CNN-based classifier to predict PD from GC-IPL thickness maps on a gender (but not age) matched cohort with AUC 0.63 but wide 95% Confidence Interval of 0.40-0.84 (Richardson et al., 2024). These mixed results underline the challenges associated with extracting PD-specific signal from retinal images.

5 FUTURE WORK

As future work, we will explore two more approaches to PD prediction from retinal images (and data, in general), corresponding to Deliverables D2.9 (M36) and D2.10 (M48).

In order to avoid the aforementioned shortcut of learning age as a proxy, we will develop further methods on the age and gender matched cohort. As we have shown, after

matching for age, Deep Learning models are unable use it as a proxy for PD classification, removing the confounding effect of age from our analysis. Consequently, we will experiment with additional methods to better extract PD-specific signal from the OCT images (and related data modalities).

Specifically, for D2.9, we will consider different training strategies: different foundation models, Multi-Instance Learning, where supervision is provided at volume level and b-scan level predictions are aggregated during training, or Multi-Task Learning, where additional tasks are jointly learned together with PD diagnosis to help learn meaning features and provide additional supervisory signal. We will also consider only training on “advanced” PD cases (e.g., images taken only after 3+ years from earliest diagnosis), which we hypothesize could strengthen the PD-related signal by providing clearer division between controls and advanced PD patients. Finally, we will explore adding more data modalities (e.g., clinical notes or EHR information) to provide stronger supervision and add PD-related signal. Clinical notes will add information about a patient’s history and comorbidities, potentially aiding our vision models into finding relationships with retinal biomarkers. Similarly, EHR information provides more context for our models to learn from. We will compare our multi-modal approach with single modality models to evaluate the incremental benefit of multi-modality.

Later, for D2.10, we will explore Federated Learning to further strengthen the PD-related signal and improve generalizability of our models. In fact, by sharing model weights with other institutions, we can not only produce a model better suited to be used on different patient populations, but we can effectively strengthen the supervisory signal by reusing what was learned at other sites.

Success of our experiments will be quantitatively measured using AUC (as done in this deliverable) as well as sensitivity and specificity. In addition, other success criteria include: the ability to identify a subgroup of PD cases for which our model works well (e.g., advanced cases) and unveiling interpretable, possibly novel retinal biomarkers associated with PD (for this, we will leverage model interpretation techniques such as SHAP) (Lundberg & Lee, 2017).

REFERENCES

Key	Reference
He et al. 2016	He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., & Sun, J. (2016). Deep residual learning for image recognition. <i>Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> , 770–778. https://doi.org/10.1109/cvpr.2016.90
Huang et al. 2024	Huang, Y., Cheung, C. Y., Li, D., Tham, Y. C., Sheng, B., Cheng, C. Y., Wang, Y. X., & Wong, T. Y. (2024). AI-integrated ocular imaging for predicting cardiovascular disease: Advancements and future outlook. <i>Eye</i> , 38(3), 464–472. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41433-023-02724-4
Jo et al. 2019	Jo, T., Nho, K., & Saykin, A. J. (2019). Deep Learning in Alzheimer's Disease: Diagnostic Classification and Prognostic Prediction Using Neuroimaging Data. <i>Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience</i> , 11, 220. https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2019.00220
Khan et al. 2022	Khan, N. C., Perera, C., Dow, E. R., Chen, K. M., Mahajan, V. B., Mruthyunjaya, P., Do, D. V., Leng, T., & Myung, D. (2022). Predicting systemic health features from retinal fundus images using transfer-learning-based artificial intelligence models. <i>Diagnostics</i> , 12(7), 1714.
Lundberg & Lee 2017	Lundberg, S. M., & Lee, S.-I. (2017). A Unified Approach to Interpreting Model Predictions. <i>Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems</i> , 30. https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2017/hash/8a20a8621978632d76c43dfd28b67767-Abstract.html
Ma et al. 2024	Ma, J., He, Y., Li, F., Han, L., You, C., & Wang, B. (2024). Segment anything in medical images. <i>Nature Communications</i> , 15(1), 654. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-44824-z
Richardson et al. 2024	Richardson, A., Kundu, A., Henao, R., Lee, T., Scott, B. L., Grewal, D. S., & Fekrat, S. (2024). Multimodal Retinal Imaging Classification for Parkinson's Disease Using a Convolutional Neural Network. <i>Translational Vision Science & Technology</i> , 13(8), 23. https://doi.org/10.1167/tvst.13.8.23
Rim et al. 2020	Rim, T. H., Lee, G., Kim, Y., Tham, Y.-C., Lee, C. J., Baik, S. J., Kim, Y. A., Yu, M., Deshmukh, M., Lee, B. K., Park, S., Kim, H. C., Sabayanagam, C., Ting, D. S. W., Wang, Y. X., Jonas, J. B., Kim, S. S., Wong, T. Y., & Cheng, C.-Y. (2020). Prediction of systemic biomarkers from retinal photographs: Development and validation of deep-learning algorithms. <i>The Lancet Digital Health</i> , 2(10), e526–e536. https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(20)30216-8
Robbins et al. 2021	Robbins, C. B., Thompson, A. C., Bhullar, P. K., Koo, H. Y., Agrawal, R., Soundararajan, S., Yoon, S. P., Polascik, B. W., Scott, B. L., Grewal, D. S., & Fekrat, S. (2021). Characterization of Retinal Microvascular and Choroidal Structural Changes in Parkinson Disease. <i>JAMA Ophthalmology</i> , 139(2), 182. https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaophthalmol.2020.5730
Su et al. 2025	Su, D., Cui, Y., He, C., Yin, P., Bai, R., Zhu, J., Lam, J. S. T., Zhang, J., Yan, R., Zheng, X., Wu, J., Zhao, D., Wang, A., Zhou, M., & Feng, T. (2025). Projections for prevalence of Parkinson's disease and its driving factors in 195 countries and territories to 2050: Modelling study of Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. <i>BMJ</i> , 388, e080952. https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-080952

Key	Reference
Tolosa et al. 2021	Tolosa, E., Garrido, A., Scholz, S. W., & Poewe, W. (2021). Challenges in the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease. <i>The Lancet Neurology</i> , 20(5), 385–397. https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(21)00030-2
Wagner et al. 2023	Wagner, S. K., Romero-Bascones, D., Cortina-Borja, M., Williamson, D. J., Struyven, R. R., Zhou, Y., Patel, S., Weil, R. S., Antoniadis, C. A., Topol, E. J., Korot, E., Foster, P. J., Balaskas, K., Ayala, U., Barrenechea, M., Gabilondo, I., Schapira, A. H. V., Khawaja, A. P., Patel, P. J., ... Zheng, Y. (2023). Retinal Optical Coherence Tomography Features Associated With Incident and Prevalent Parkinson Disease. <i>Neurology</i> , 101(16). https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.0000000000207727
Willis et al. 2022	Willis, A. W., Roberts, E., Beck, J. C., Fiske, B., Ross, W., Savica, R., Van Den Eeden, S. K., Tanner, C. M., & Marras, C. (2022). Incidence of Parkinson disease in North America. <i>Npj Parkinson's Disease</i> , 8(1), 1–7. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41531-022-00410-y
Zhou et al. 2023	Zhou, Y., Chia, M. A., Wagner, S. K., Ayhan, M. S., Williamson, D. J., Struyven, R. R., Liu, T., Xu, M., Lozano, M. G., Woodward-Court, P., Kihara, Y., UK Biobank Eye & Vision Consortium, Allen, N., Gallacher, J. E. J., Littlejohns, T., Aslam, T., Bishop, P., Black, G., Sergouniotis, P., ... Keane, P. A. (2023). A foundation model for generalizable disease detection from retinal images. <i>Nature</i> , 622(7981), 156–163. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06555-x